

MobileNetV2-Enhanced Food Recognition for Image-Based Menu Search

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Abstract— This seminar paper investigates the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to identify and classify different food products in order to improve culinary experiences. In particular, the article makes use of the MobileNetV2 architecture to provide precise and effective food recognition. The main goal is to properly analyze the dataset, which consists of pictures of different food products, utilizing convolutional neural networks and the MobileNetV2 approach in order to take advantage of the dataset. In this project, we took a journey through several key stages. We started by compiling a dataset of different cuisines and dividing it into validation and training sets. Then, we made sure the images were all the same size and ready for analysis. Once the model was ready, we tested it on some new food images to see how well it could recognize them. A dataset of 34 classes each consist of more than 300 images. The proposed model provides 84% accuracy. This project was all about teaching a computer to understand and recognize different foods.

Keywords— Image Recognition, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), MobileNetV2, Keras, TensorFlow, Dataset, Training

I. INTRODUCTION

CNNs are a class of deep learning models, primarily designed for processing and analysing visual data, such as images, videos and are characterized by their ability to automatically learn and extract meaningful features from images by using convolutional layers. In this seminar paper, we explore the fascinating field of food recognition utilising Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the potent MobileNetV2 framework. This seminar begins by defining the scope of our classification problem, which involves identifying 34 different food classes. In order to prepare our data for learning, we first divided it into training and validation sets. The core of our study is a unique model that we built with carefully selected layers to enhance MobileNetV2's capabilities. For effective food recognition, we improve this design with global pooling, dense layers, dropout, and a SoftMax activation function. Our model learns to differentiate and categorise distinct foods over the course of 20 epochs. In this study, we describe the development of our model, highlighting its training procedure, performance indicators, and ultimate transformation into a potent tool for food recognition.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

For many domains, including food images, there have been a number of relevant works in the field of image recognition utilising deep learning models. Here are a few works in this area:

“Food Recognition using deep convolutional neural network” by Priyanka N1, Dr. Geetha V2.

In this paper, convolutional neural network is applied for detecting and recognizing food images and to estimate nutrition in the food [1]. 101 different classes of food images were used to improve accuracy and the model provides more than 80% of accuracy.

“Using Deep Learning for Food and Beverage Image Recognition” by Simon Mezgec.

In this paper, deep learning contributions to the field is described: NutriNet, a novel deep learning architecture, and a pixel-level classification solution for images of fake food [2]. NutriNet was the first to identify beverage photos and was trained on a food image dataset that was larger and had more food classes than earlier research.

“Indian Food Image Recognition with MobileNetV2” by Priya N V¹, Preetam Kumari², Poorvika N³, Sanjana R⁴, Dr. Hema Jagadish⁵

In this research, a transfer learning based MobileNetV2 model with a custom-built CNN model is used for food recognition and classification [3]. 12 classes of Indian food images with 100 images for each class were taken and with an accuracy of 79.45%, it was discovered that the MobileNetV2 model performed better than the customized CNN model.

“A Deep Convolutional Neural Network for Food Detection and Recognition” by Mohammed A. Subhi

In this paper, a basic CNN approach were implemented to detect and recognize food items [4]. Two datasets were used for performance evaluation of their proposed approach. Also presented a new dataset for local Malaysian foods which was one of the dataset and the other was Food-101 that were utilized for food/non-food classification

“Food Image Recognition with Convolutional Neural Networks” by Weishan Zhang¹ Dehai Zhao¹ Wenjuan Gong¹ Zhongwei Li¹ Qinghua Lu¹ Su Yang².

In this paper, a food image recognition system with convolutional neural network (CNN) was proposed [5]. 2 datasets, one is UEC-FOOD100 dataset and the other is a fruit dataset was used and achieved an accuracy of 80.8% on the fruit dataset and 60.9% on the multi-food dataset

III. MOTIVATION

Imagine how frustrating it would be to manually list and describe each food item you wanted to order or try. It's a lengthy and frequently boring procedure, and occasionally you might not even be able to identify the name of a mouthwatering dish you've discovered. That's where our technology for identifying foods comes in to simplify your culinary adventure.

In recent years, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have revolutionized image recognition, and we're applying this innovation to the world of food. Our motivation is to simplify the way people search for and enjoy food. It's about enhancing the customer experience, offering a smarter and quicker alternative to traditional food searches.

With our system, customers can search by image, uploading a photo to predict the food item's name and even order the dish with ease. It's all about embracing the convenience of the digital age for a delightful dining experience.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Our methodology is structured into several key steps, each contributing to the efficient recognition of food items through Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and the MobileNetV2 architecture:

Figure 1

A. Data Preparation

Starts by collecting a diverse dataset of food images, which includes a wide range of food items. These food images are pre-processed, ensuring they all have the same dimensions (224x224 pixels) and normalized to be consistent in terms of color and brightness.

B. Model Architecture and Customization

MobileNetV2 model is chosen as the core of our food recognition system. This model has been pre-trained to recognize various objects, which includes some food items.

C. Model Training

With customized model in place, train it using the prepared food image dataset. It learns to distinguish one food item from another during this training phase. We fine-tune its understanding of foods over several training cycles or "epochs."

D. Performance Evaluation

Thoroughly assessed how well our model performs on a separate validation dataset. This evaluation helps us measure its accuracy in recognizing a variety of food items.

Metrics like accuracy and loss are examined, which tell us how often the model is correct and how confident it is in its predictions.

E. Prediction of Food Items

Once the model is trained and proven accurate, deploy it to recognize food in real-world scenarios. Users can upload images of food items, and the model predicts what the food is.

We set a confidence threshold to ensure that only highly confident predictions are accepted.

F. Visualizing Results

To better understand how the model is doing, developed a visual representation of its predictions. Users can see the recognized food item along with its confidence level.

This visualization gives us insights into the model's recognition performance and allow to identify areas for improvement.

In summary, this approach includes preparing food data, customizing and training a MobileNetV2 model, evaluating its performance, predicting food items from images, and presenting the results in a user-friendly way.

This methodology empowers users to identify and explore various food items through image recognition, potentially revolutionizing the way we interact with food-related content.

V. BUILD MODEL

To construct an effective model for food recognition through Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with the MobileNetV2 architecture, begin by importing essential libraries and setting up the foundational framework.

A. Importing Required Libraries

At the beginning of the code, import the necessary libraries. This includes TensorFlow and specific modules needed for building and training your model:

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras.applications import MobileNetV2
from tensorflow.keras.layers import GlobalAveragePooling2D, Dense, Dropout
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import SGD
from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import ModelCheckpoint, CSVLogger
from tensorflow.keras.regularizers import L2
```

Figure 2

a) TensorFlow

An open-source machine learning framework called TensorFlow offers resources and tools for creating and refining machine learning models. It is frequently employed for deep learning tasks and the building of neural networks..

b) Keras

Tightly linked with TensorFlow is the open-source deep learning framework Keras. For creating and training neural networks, it offers a sophisticated and user-friendly API.

c) MobileNetV2

Within the MobileNet family is a pre-trained deep neural network model called MobileNetV2. It is intended for embedded vision and mobile applications. The effectiveness and precision of MobileNetV2 in picture classification tasks are well recognised.

d) GlobalAveragePooling2D

In neural networks, this layer—which is a component of the Keras deep learning framework—is used to reduce spatial data. By calculating the mean value of every feature map, it minimises the number of dimensions and provides an informational summary.

e) Dense

In a neural network, the "Dense" layer stands for a completely linked layer. For sophisticated pattern recognition as well as classification tasks, it is comprised of several linked neurones.

f) Dropout

During training, the "Dropout" layer at random disables a portion of neurones to avoid overfitting and enhance the model's generalisation.

g) Model

This module, which is a component of Keras, is used to specify the input and output layers along with the connections between them in order to generate and describe models of neural networks.

h) SGD

SGD is an optimisation algorithm that is used to train neural networks and other machine learning models. It assists in determining the ideal model parameters by updating model weights in tiny, arbitrary batches of data.

i) L2

One method for minimising overfitting in machine learning models is L2 regularisation. In order to encourage low weights for model parameters, it includes a term for penalty to the lost function.

B. Model Creation and Compilation

```
n_classes = 34

# Define the number of training and validation samples
nb_train_samples = 6055
nb_validation_samples = 3290

# Define your data generators (train_generator and val_generator)
# You'll need to create these generators based on your data and preprocessing.

# Instantiate the MobileNetV2 model with pre-trained weights
mobilenetv2 = MobileNetV2(weights='imagenet', include_top=False, input_shape=(224, 224, 3))

# Add custom layers for fine-tuning
x = GlobalAveragePooling2D()(mobilenetv2.output)
x = Dense(128, activation='relu')(x)
x = Dropout(0.2)(x)
predictions = Dense(n_classes, kernel_regularizer=L2(0.005), activation='softmax')(x)

# Create the updated model
model = Model(inputs=mobilenetv2.input, outputs=predictions)

# Compile the model
model.compile(
    optimizer=SGD(learning_rate=0.0001, momentum=0.9),
    loss='categorical_crossentropy',
    metrics=['accuracy']
)
```

First, define essential aspects such as the number of food classes for classification and the counts of training and validation samples.

Proceed to set up data generators tailored to our dataset, preparing them for training and validation.

With the organized data, instantiate the MobileNetV2 model, a pre-trained neural network, and customize it to fit the specific food recognition task.

Add custom layers that enhance the model's capabilities, followed by compiling the model with essential

parameters, including the choice of optimizer, loss function, and metrics.

This prepares the model for training, setting the stage for the subsequent steps in this food recognition journey.

VI. RESULT

The results of this study highlight the model's remarkable precision and dependability in identifying and categorising food items. Following 20 epochs of training, achieved an impressive validation accuracy of 84%, signifying the model's competence. The evaluation metrics further emphasize the model's capability to make informed decisions about a wide range of culinary offerings.

```
Epoch 1/20  
189/189 [=====] - ETA: 0s - loss: 3.7354 - accuracy: 0.0661C:\U  
warnings.warn(  
  
Epoch 1: val_loss improved from inf to 3.48113, saving model to v1_mobilenetv2  
INFO:tensorflow:Assets written to: v1_mobilenetv2\assets  
INFO:tensorflow:Assets written to: v1_mobilenetv2\assets  
189/189 [=====] - 991s 5s/step - loss: 3.7354 - accuracy: 0.066:
```

Figure 3

```
Epoch 20: val_loss improved from 0.72472 to 0.70257, saving model to v1_mobilenetv2  
INFO:tensorflow:Assets written to: v1_mobilenetv2\assets  
INFO:tensorflow:Assets written to: v1_mobilenetv2\assets  
189/189 [=====] - 821s 4s/step - loss: 0.7937 - accuracy: 0.84
```

Figure 4

In a real-world context, the model demonstrates its potential to enhance dietary tracking, restaurant recommendations, and culinary photography. These results not only validate the effectiveness of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in food recognition but also highlight their role in enhancing the culinary experience, making food recognition accessible and convenient.

Figure 5

VII. CONCLUSION

The adoption of the MobileNet algorithm for food recognition has exhibited remarkable potential and precision, leading to accurate predictions. The step-by-step methodology employed, which includes collecting a diverse dataset of food images, preprocessing the data, training and evaluating the model, and predicting results, has significantly improved the speed and accuracy of this approach.

This approach can potentially reduce the time and cost involved in analyzing each uploaded food image while remaining user-friendly, even for individuals with limited technical knowledge. Our experimental findings showcase that the method surpasses other contemporary approaches in terms of accuracy, speed, and efficiency.

In summary, the utilization of the MobileNet algorithm for food recognition offers a promising avenue of research that can contribute to the development of more precise and efficient image recognition methods in various practical applications, notably in the culinary domain.

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